

Taxonomic Revision of Genus *Oligonyx* Saussure, 1869 (Mantodea: Thespidae: Thespinae: Thespini)

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Abstract. Taxonomic revision of the genus *Oligonyx* Saussure, 1869. Four new species are proposed, including *amentari* n. sp. from Hispaniola, *chactas* n. sp. from Cozumel Island, and *nebulosus* n. sp. and *undulicoxa* n. sp. from Honduras. Additionally, *dohrnianus* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 and *gryps* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 are rendered *nomen dubium*.

Oligonyx Saussure, 1869 is a poorly understood genus, suffering from a long history of misclassification, diagnostic instability, and systematic neglect. This genus was burdened from its inception with an ambiguous foundation: its type species (*bicornis*) was designated from a nymph, while subsequent species were described from an adult female (*bidens*), a damaged male (*maya*), and two syntypes (*gryps*) that represent entirely separate taxa (*bicornis* and *bidens*). Compounding these taxonomic challenges is the unstable historical classification of *Oligonyx*, which has undergone multiple diagnostic shifts that shuffled unrelated taxa into the genus while simultaneously separating true conspecific members into different genera based solely on sexually dimorphic characters. This has led to mass confusion, with traditional dichotomous keys rendered inaccurate or entirely unusable due to the poorly defined species limits of *Oligonyx*. Additionally, many past treatments of the genus relied on outdated, erroneous diagnostic characters, failing to incorporate key morphological traits such as prozona-to-metazona ratios, forefemoral shape and maculation, and prothoracic leg spination, which are now found to be critical for genus and species identification.

Despite its historical obscurity, *Oligonyx* is actually a distinct and more diverse genus than previously recognized, comprising both widespread species and locally restricted taxa, several of which remain undescribed. The previously assumed low species diversity was underestimated, with disparate populations being erroneously classified under one of the few, poorly defined original species. This is largely due to the biogeographical complexity of the region in which *Oligonyx* occurs, which presents drastically different ecological conditions—including elevation metrics, tropical humid versus tropical dry forests, and coastal versus alpine habitats. *Oligonyx* primarily occurs in the tropical humid forest ecoregions of eastern and southern Mexico, extending along the Gulf of America and deep into Central America, as far south as Nicaragua. It is replaced by *Bistanta* Anderson, 2018 in the tropical dry forests and temperate sierras of central and northern Mexico, where *Bistanta* extends northward into the North American deserts and Great Plains. The geographic ranges of these two genera suggest potential overlap and their morphological similarity raises questions about their taxonomic validity. A molecular study

would be useful to determine whether *Oligonyx* and *Bistanta* truly represent separate genera or if they form part of a broader continuum of variation within a single lineage.

Adding further complexity to the distribution of *Oligonyx* is a recent and unexpected discovery that challenges prior assumptions about its range. Previously thought to be endemic to southern Mexico and Central America, *Oligonyx* has now been documented in Hispaniola, marking its first confirmed occurrence in the Caribbean. This raises new questions about the genus' historical biogeography and suggests that additional, undiscovered populations may exist on other Caribbean islands, particularly in areas that have not been thoroughly surveyed for mantodean diversity. Given the ecological variability across Nicaragua and Costa Rica, and the historical misclassification of *Oligonyx* species with other genera, it is also likely that several undescribed species of *Oligonyx* exist further into Central America.

Members of *Oligonyx* exhibit a remarkable twig-mimicry adaptation, blending seamlessly into their environment with an elongated, brown-colored habitus that closely resembles small twigs. This mimicry is enhanced by their behavioral posture, as both sexes frequently rest with their forelegs held together and extended in front of their head, further reinforcing their resemblance to broken twigs. Males and females occupy different microhabitats that maximize their camouflage; males are more commonly found on lower-story forest foliage, where their slender, winged bodies allow them to move between perches, while females, being flightless, are more frequently encountered on the ground among leaf litter or resting on the lower reaches of tree trunks, where their cryptic coloration is most effective. The disparity in mobility between the sexes also influences collection methods—males are frequently attracted to artificial lights at night and can be readily captured using light traps, whereas females are less commonly encountered due to their ground-dwelling habits and lack of flight. This ecological partitioning between sexes plays a role in their dispersal and population dynamics, contributing to the genus' diverse yet often localized distribution across its range.

The general morphology of *Oligonyx* reflects its highly specialized twig-mimicry, not only in its overall body shape and coloration but also in the structural adaptations of the head capsule and forelegs, which play critical roles in both camouflage and prey capture. One of the most distinctive cranial features of the genus is the concave vertex of the head capsule, which can range from shallowly to deeply recessed, accompanied by juxtaocular lobes that form conical protrusions on either side. This configuration allows individuals to tilt their head upward, fitting the vertex neatly into the anterior margin of the prozona, effectively breaking up the contour of the body to enhance their twig-like resemblance. This adaptation is particularly useful in their preferred resting posture, where the extended forelegs and elongated body contribute to their cryptic appearance.

Beyond its role in mimicry, the foreleg morphology of *Oligonyx* presents an unusual predatory adaptation, which has long puzzled entomologists. Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 175) wrote, "It would be interesting to know how these insects capture their prey, and for what purpose the inner spines have their points recurved against the tibia, so as apparently to render them useless." This observation suggests that the foretibial spines do not conform to the typical raptorial grasping mechanism seen in most mantises, where the tibiae fold tightly into the femora to immobilize prey. Instead, *Oligonyx* and closely related genera exhibit a stabbing or hooking strategy, a hypothesis that was reinvigorated by Anderson (2018: 270) when discussing *Thesprotia* Stål, 1877, a closely allied genus with nearly identical foretibial morphology. Anderson noted, "Unlike the typical foreleg morphology of larger mantises where the foretibiae clasp into the forefemora to simply immobilize prey trapped in between the two appendages until they are consumed, the foretibiae of *Thesprotia* are used to stab or hook into the prey's body, which creates an interesting alternative to prey capture." Subsequent studies have provided additional evidence supporting this impaling hypothesis as a novel hunting strategy, with Rivera & Callohuari (2019) corroborating the observation across multiple genera within Thespini. This stabbing method, rather than a simple clasping strategy, enables *Oligonyx* and similar genera to subdue relatively large prey items, particularly

soft-bodied insects, by piercing them with their modified foretibial spines. This capability expands their prey selection beyond what would typically be expected for a mantis of their size. Thus, the morphology of *Oligonyx*—from its head structure that enhances crypsis to its specialized predatory appendages—demonstrates a unique convergence of camouflage and function, allowing these mantises to thrive within their forested habitats while employing an alternative and highly effective prey capture method.

This revision seeks to resolve the long-standing taxonomic confusion surrounding *Oligonyx* by: reassessing historical descriptions and taxonomic placements, re-evaluating species limits, incorporating new material from underrepresented regions and providing a functional key for males that accurately reflects species diversity and diagnoses that are presently known. Through this revision, *Oligonyx* can be taxonomically stabilized, allowing for future studies to properly recognize its true diversity and biogeographical distribution.

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Oligonyx Saussure, 1869

Description. Habitus small, elongated. Pigmentation of both sexes uniformly light to dark brown, occasionally spotted with darker pigmentation. Head capsule small, slightly narrowed. Male vertex flat to shallowly concave, positioned just higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Female vertex concave, positioned significantly higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Juxtaocular bulges prominent, strongly conical in both sexes, more pronounced and divergent in female. Ocelli prominent in male, significantly more reduced in female. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Compound eyes large, rounded in male, more elliptical in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous; ciliated in male, simple in female. Pronotum elongated and slender, supracoxal dilation weakly developed to marked, anterior margin of prozona narrowly rounded, lateral pronotal margins with fine denticulation throughout, stouter in female. Metazona measures 1.9-2.8 times as long as prozona. Pronotal surface smooth to slightly granulated, finely keeled, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Prothoracic legs very slender, elongated. Forecoxae as long as or shorter than metazona, apical lobes divergent. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae slightly lamellar, somewhat compressed and sinuate beyond middle. Forefemora very slender, armed on apical half with 4 posteroventral, 3-4 discoidal, 7 anteroventral spines. Discoidal spines moderately long; fourth discoidal spine, when present, diminutive. Anteroventral spines 6 and 7 separated by long gap. Tibial spur groove placed in approximate middle of forefemora. Foretibiae very significantly shortened, rounded, tibial spur reaching second discoidal spine at repose; armed with 1 posteroventral and 3-6 anteroventral spines. Posteroventral spine slightly to strongly curved in male, recumbent, either overlapping or acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Posteroventral spine strongly curved and recumbent in female, parallel to and apart from tibial spur; penultimate 3 anteroventral spines large, recumbent but apart from tibial base. Meso/metathoracic legs very long, thin. Femora and tibiae slender throughout, pigmented various shades of brown, often with darker annulation or faint distal darkening. Basitarsi extraordinarily long, measuring significantly longer than remaining tarsomeres combined. Male wings reach abdominal tergite V-VI, leaving remaining abdominal segments and terminalia exposed. Forewings narrow, costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area iridescent hyaline, tinted light to dark brown. Primary venation brown, venules hyaline with points of insertion brown. Stigma absent. Hindwings iridescent hyaline, tinted light to dark brown, discoidal area darker. Female wingless. Abdomen long and cylindrical in both sexes. Supra-anal plate elongate, triangular. Cerci elongated, significantly surpassing subgenital plate, cylindrical-tapered.

Distribution. Southern Mexico, Central America and Hispaniola

Type Species: *Oligonyx bicornis* Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist:

- Oligonyx armentari* n. sp.
- Oligonyx bicornis* Saussure, 1869
- Oligonyx bidens* (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)
- Oligonyx chactas* n. sp.
- Oligonyx maya* (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)
- Oligonyx nebulosus* n. sp.
- Oligonyx undulicoxa* n. sp.

Key to *Oligonyx* Males:

- 1 Forefemora very elongated and thin, measuring >11 times longer than basal width 2
- 1' Forefemora slender, moderately narrowed, measuring <11 times longer than basal width 3
- 2 Forefemora measures >13 times longer than basal width, metazona measures 2.0 times longer than prozona. Precinctive to Hispaniola *O. armentari*
- 2 Forefemora measures <12 times longer than basal width, metazona measures 2.4 times longer than prozona. Occurs in Central America *O. bidens*
- 3 Metazona measures >2 times longer than prozona. Prothoracic coxae measure ≥ 5 mm in length, prothoracic femora measure ≥ 6.5 mm in length 4
- 3' Metazona measures <2 times longer than prozona. Prothoracic coxae measure ≤ 4 mm in length, prothoracic femora measure ≤ 5 mm in length *O. maya*
- 4 Forecoxae shorter than metazona. Occurs in Central America or Cozumel Island 5
- 4' Forecoxae equivalent in length to metazona. Occurs in eastern and southern Mexico mainland
..... *O. bicornis*
- 5 Forefemora measures <10.5 times longer than basal width. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae simple throughout, anterior surface colored light brown with scattered blackish mottling 6
- 5' Forefemora measures >10.5 times longer than basal width. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae distally expanded into low lobe, anterior surface colored dark brown with concentrated blackish mottling *O. undulicoxa*
- 6 Posteroventral spine of foretibiae overlapping tibial spur. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown, transitioning to darker brown distally, mottled with black throughout. Precinctive to Cozumel Island *O. chactas*
- 6' Posteroventral spine of foretibiae acutely angled away from tibial spur. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown with blackish mottling concentrated basally into irregular blotch. Occurs in alpine regions of Central America *O. nebulosus*

Anterior surface of male prothoracic legs: *armentari* (top left), *bidens* (top right), *chactas* (center left), *nebulosus* (center right), *undulicoxa* (bottom)

Oligonyx armentari n. sp.

Type Material. ♂ Holotype: 18°05'18"N 71°16'31"W: Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic 06.02.2024 CSMolinari & MArmenteros leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Description. *Habitus* small, elongated. Pigmentation uniformly dark brown in male, grayish-brown in female.

Head capsule. Male vertex flat, positioned just higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Juxtaocular bulges prominent. Ocelli prominent in male. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Compound eyes large, rounded in male, more elliptical in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous; ciliated in male, simple in female.

Pronotum elongated and slender, supracoxal dilation marked, anterior margin of prozona narrowly rounded, lateral pronotal margins with fine denticulation throughout. Metazona measures 2.0 times as long as prozona in male. Pronotal surface smooth, finely keeled, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Pronotum pigmented dark brown in male; light grayish-brown with blackish punctation in female.

Prothoracic legs very slender, elongated. Forecoxae as long as metazona in male. Forefemora very slender, armed on apical half with 4 posteroventral, 3 discoidal, 7 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae very significantly shortened, rounded, tibial spur reaching second discoidal spine at repose; armed with 1 posteroventral and 3 anteroventral spines. Posteroventral spine slightly curved in male, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae mottled with dark brown throughout in male, concentrated basally. Anterior surface of forefemora maculated with blackish stripe that extends from base to discoidal spines in male, surrounded by dark brown mottling.

Meso/metathoracic legs very long, thin. Femora and tibiae slender throughout, pigmented light brown with darker annulation, distal darkening. Basitarsi extraordinarily long, measuring significantly longer than remaining tarsomeres combined.

Wings reach abdominal tergite V in male, leaving remaining abdominal segments and terminalia exposed. Forewings narrow, costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown. Primary venation brown, venules hyaline with points of insertion brown. Stigma absent. Hindwings iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown, discoidal area darker. Female wingless.

Abdomen long and cylindrical. Supra-anal plate elongate, extended, triangular, extended 1.4 times longer than width in male. Cerci elongated, significantly surpassing subgenital plate, cylindrical-tapered. Abdomen pigmented dark brown in male; light grayish-brown with median blackish blotch in female.

Etymology. The specific epithet "armentari" is a patronym to Maribel Armenteros.

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.0 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented uniformly dark brown. Forefemora measures 13.9 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, mottled with dark brown throughout, maculation concentrated basally. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with blackish stripe that extends from base to discoidal spines, surrounded by dark brown mottling. Precinctive to Hispaniola.

Type Locality. Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic

Distribution. Hispaniola

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 39.5; pronotum length 9.5; prozona length 3; metazona length 6; forewing length 19.5; prothoracic coxa length 6; prothoracic femur length 7.5; metathoracic femur length 8.

Oligonyx bicornis Saussure, 1869

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.1 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented uniformly dark brown. Forefemora measures 10.9 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, transitioning to darker brown distally, sparsely punctated with dark brown throughout. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with larger patches of dark brown. Occurs in eastern Mexico along the Gulf of America and southern Mexico mainland.

Holotype: ♂ Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva

Type Locality. Tehuantepec, Oaxaca, Mexico

Distribution. Mexico

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 41.5; pronotum length 7-11; prozona length 2.5; metazona length 5; forewing length 15.5-22; prothoracic coxa length 5; prothoracic femur length 6.5. *Female.* Body length 42; pronotum length 12-12.5.

Oligonyx bidens (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.4 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented uniformly dark brown. Forefemora measures 11.4 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, transitioning to darker brown distally, punctated with dark brown throughout. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with broken blackish stripe that extends from base to discoidal spines, surrounded by dark brown mottling. Female: Metazona measures 2.5 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented uniformly brown. Forefemora measures 11.4 times longer than basal width. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, maculated with black median stripe throughout most of its length. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with uneven blackish stripe that extends from discoidal spines to base. Occurs in Mesoamerican Gulf-Caribbean tropical humid forests of northern Honduras, Belize, northern Guatemala and southern Quintana Roo.

Holotype: ♀ Natural History Museum, London

Type Locality. Roatán Island, Honduras

Distribution. Belize, Guatemala, Honduras and Mexico

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 37-44.5; pronotum length 9-11; prozona length 2.5-3; metazona length 6.5-8; forewing length 18-22; prothoracic coxa length 5.5-6.5; prothoracic femur length 7-8. *Female.* Body length 46-53; pronotum length 15-17; prothoracic coxa length 8.5-9; prothoracic femur length 9.5-11; metathoracic femur length 9.5.

Oligonyx chaectas **n. sp.**

Type Material. ♂ Holotype: 20°25' N 86°55' W: Cozumel Island, Quintana Roo, Mexico 07.2020 JMedin leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas. ♀ Allotype: 20°25' N 86°55' W: Cozumel Island, Quintana Roo, Mexico 07.2020 JMedin leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Description. *Habitus* small, elongated. Pigmentation light brown with dark brown maculation.

Head capsule. Male vertex shallowly concave, positioned just higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Female vertex concave, positioned significantly higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Juxtaocular bulges prominent, strongly conical in both sexes, more pronounced and divergent in female. Ocelli prominent in male, vestigial in female. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Compound eyes large, rounded in male, more elliptical in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous; ciliated in male, simple in female.

Pronotum elongated and slender, supracoxal dilation marked, anterior margin of prozona narrowly rounded, lateral pronotal margins with fine denticulation throughout. Metazona measures 2.3 times as long as prozona in male, 1.9 times as long in female. Pronotal surface smooth, finely keeled, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Pronotum pigmented brown with heavy dark brown mottling in male; light brown with two heavy blackish stripes running length of metazona in female.

Prothoracic legs very slender, elongated. Forecoxae shorter than metazona in male; equivalent in female. Forefemora very slender, armed on apical half with 4 posteroventral, 3 discoidal, 7 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae very significantly shortened, rounded, tibial spur reaching second discoidal spine at repose; armed with 1 posteroventral and 3 anteroventral spines. Posteroventral spine strongly curved in male, recumbent, overlapping tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Posteroventral spine strongly curved and recumbent in female, parallel to and apart from tibial spur; anteroventral spines large, recumbent but apart from tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown, transitioning to darker brown distally, mottled with black throughout in male, more scantily

punctated in female. Anterior surface of forefemora colored light brown, maculated with four dark brown blotches in male, female maculated with three dark brown blotches that form broken stripe at base of discoidal spines.

Meso/metathoracic legs very long, thin. Femora and tibiae slender throughout, pigmented light brown with faint annulation. Basitarsi extraordinarily long, measuring significantly longer than remaining tarsomeres combined.

Wings reach abdominal tergite V in male, leaving remaining abdominal segments and terminalia exposed. Forewings narrow, costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown. Primary venation brown, venules hyaline with points of insertion brown. Stigma absent. Hindwings iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown, discoidal area darker. Female wingless.

Abdomen long and cylindrical. Supra-anal plate triangular, extended 1.1 times longer than width. Cerci elongated, significantly surpassing subgenital plate, cylindrical-tapered.

Etymology. The specific epithet “chactas” is derived from Chaac, the Yucatec Mayan name for the rain and thunder god, combined with the Latin suffix -tas, forming a noun meaning “of Chaac” or “Chaac’s entity,” rendered as a noun in apposition to honor the species’ discovery on Cozumel Island during the rainy month of July.

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.3 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented brown with heavy dark brown mottling. Forefemora measures 9.8 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine strongly curved in male, recumbent, overlapping tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, punctated with dark brown throughout, maculation concentrated distally. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with four dark brown blotches. Female: Metazona measures 1.9 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented light brown with two heavy blackish stripes running length of metazona. Forefemora measures 10.3 times longer than basal width. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, transitioning to darker brown distally, scanty punctated with dark brown. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with three dark brown blotches that form broken stripe at base of discoidal spines. Precinctive to Cozumel Island.

Type Locality. Cozumel Island, Quintana Roo, Mexico

Distribution. Cozumel Island

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 43; pronotum length 11; prozona length 3; metazona length 8; forewing length 19; prothoracic coxa length 6.5; prothoracic femur length 8; metathoracic femur length 9.5. *Female.* Body length 38; pronotum length 11.5; prozona length 4; metazona length 7.5; prothoracic coxa length 7.5; prothoracic femur length 8.5; metathoracic femur length 9.

Oligonyx maya (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 1.9 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented light brown, mottled with darker brown. Forefemora measures 10.9 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae light brown, punctated with dark brown throughout. Anterior surface of forefemora light brown, maculated with larger patches of dark brown. Occurs in tropical dry forests of northwestern Yucatán, Mexico.

Holotype: ♂ Natural History Museum, London

Type Locality. Temax, Yucatán, Mexico

Distribution. Mexico

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 37-38; pronotum length 7; prozona length 2.5; metazona length 4.5-5; forewing length 15.5; prothoracic coxa length 4; prothoracic femur length 4.5-5.

Oligonyx nebulosus n. sp.

Type Material. ♂ Holotype: 14°02'06"N 86°44'24"W: Uyuca Biological Station, Francisco Morazán, Honduras, 1,700 meters 05.01.2022 EVan de Berghe leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Description. *Habitus* small, elongated. Pigmentation light brown to gray with dark brownish-black mottling.

Head capsule. Male vertex flat, positioned just higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Juxtaocular bulges prominent. Ocelli prominent in male. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Compound eyes large, rounded in male, more elliptical in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous; ciliated in male, simple in female.

Pronotum elongated and slender, supracoxal dilation marked, anterior margin of prozona narrowly rounded, lateral pronotal margins with fine denticulation throughout. Metazona measures 2.1 times as long as prozona in male. Pronotal surface smooth, finely keeled, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Pronotum pigmented light brown to gray with dark brownish-black mottling in both sexes.

Prothoracic legs very slender, elongated. Forecoxae shorter than metazona in male. Forefemora very slender, armed on apical half with 4 posteroventral, 3 discoidal, 7 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae very significantly shortened, rounded, tibial spur reaching second discoidal spine at repose; armed with 1 posteroventral and 3 anteroventral spines. Posteroventral spine slightly curved in male, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Posteroventral spine strongly curved and recumbent in female, parallel to and apart from tibial spur; anteroventral spines large, recumbent but apart from tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown to gray with blackish mottling throughout in both sexes, concentrated basally into irregular blotch. Both sexes with anterior surface of forefemora maculated with small blackish blotch in middle, larger blackish blotch extends from discoidal spines to base.

Meso/metathoracic legs very long, thin. Femora and tibiae slender throughout, pigmented light brown. Basitarsi extraordinarily long, measuring significantly longer than remaining tarsomeres combined.

Wings. Forewings narrow in male, costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown. Primary venation brown, venules hyaline with points of insertion brown. Stigma absent. Hindwings iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown, discoidal area darker. Female wingless.

Abdomen long and cylindrical. Cerci shortened in female. Abdomen pigmented light brown to gray with dark brownish-black mottling in female. Male holotype has distal half of abdomen missing.

Etymology. The specific epithet “nebulosus” is derived from the Latin term *nebulosus*, meaning “clouded” or “blotchy,” referring to the heavily mottled pattern of the pronotum and forelegs of this alpine species, which gives this species a diffuse, clouded appearance.

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.1 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented light brown with dark brownish-black mottling. Forefemora measures 10.1 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown with blackish mottling throughout, concentrated basally into irregular blotch. Anterior surface of forefemora maculated with small blackish blotch in middle, larger blackish blotch extends from discoidal spines to base. Occurs in alpine regions of Guatemala, Honduras and Nicaragua.

Type Locality. Uyuca Biological Station, Francisco Morazán, Honduras

Distribution. Guatemala, Honduras and Nicaragua

Measurements. *Male.* Pronotum length 10.5; prozona length 3; metazona length 7.5; forewing length 19.5; prothoracic coxa length 6.5; prothoracic femur length 7.5; metathoracic femur length 8.5.

Oligonyx undulicoxa n. sp.

Type Material. ♂ Holotype: 14°55'30"N 88°02'53"W: Yojoa, Emerald Valley, Cortés, Honduras, 740 meters 12.26.2021 EVan de Berghe leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Description. *Habitus* small, elongated. Pigmentation dark brown.

Head capsule. Male vertex flat, positioned just higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Juxtaocular bulges prominent. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Compound eyes large, rounded in male, more elliptical in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous, ciliated in male; simple, annulated in female.

Pronotum elongated and slender, supracoxal dilation slight, anterior margin of prozona narrowly rounded, lateral pronotal margins with fine denticulation throughout. Metazona measures 2.8 times as long as prozona in male. Pronotal surface smooth, finely keeled, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Pronotum pigmented dark brown in male; light brown with two heavy blackish stripes running length of metazona in female.

Prothoracic legs very slender, elongated. Forecoxae shorter than metazona in male. Forefemora very slender, armed on apical half with 4 posteroventral, 3 discoidal, 7 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae very significantly shortened, rounded, tibial spur reaching second discoidal spine at repose; armed with 1 posteroventral and 5 anteroventral spines. Posteroventral spine slightly curved in male, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Posteroventral spine strongly curved and recumbent in female, parallel to and apart from tibial spur; anteroventral spines large, recumbent but apart from tibial base. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae distally expanded into low lobe, anterior surface colored dark brown with concentrated blackish mottling in male. Anterior surface of forefemora heavily mottled with blackish-brown throughout in male, mottling proximally and centrally concentrated.

Meso/metathoracic legs very long, thin. Femora and tibiae slender throughout, pigmented light brown. Basitarsi extraordinarily long, measuring significantly longer than remaining tarsomeres combined.

Wings. Forewings narrow in male, costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown. Primary venation brown, venules hyaline with points of insertion brown. Stigma absent. Hindwings iridescent hyaline, tinted light brown, discoidal area darker. Female wingless.

Abdomen long and cylindrical. Supra-anal plate triangular, extended 1.2 times longer than width. Cerci elongated, significantly surpassing subgenital plate, cylindrical-tapered.

Etymology. The specific epithet “undulicoxa” is derived from the Latin term undulus, meaning “wavy” or “undulated” and coxa, meaning “hip” or “coxal segment”, referring to the distinctively undulated and expanded anteroventral margin of the forecoxae, a key diagnostic feature of this species.

Diagnosis. Male: Metazona measures 2.8 times as long as prozona; pronotum pigmented dark brown. Forefemora measures 10.7 times longer than basal width. Posteroventral spine slightly curved, recumbent, acutely angled away from tibial spur; anteroventral spines bent into and touching tibial base. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored dark brown with concentrated blackish mottling. Anterior surface of forefemora heavily mottled with blackish-brown throughout, mottling proximally and centrally concentrated. Occurs in mid-elevation transitional zones of Honduras and El Salvador.

Type Locality. Yojoa, Emerald Valley, Cortés, Honduras

Distribution. El Salvador and Honduras

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 47.5; pronotum length 11.5; prozona length 3; metazona length 8.5; forewing length 22; prothoracic coxa length 6; prothoracic femur length 7.5; metathoracic femur length 8.5.

TAXONOMY

Taxonomic Summary. The genus *Oligonyx* currently comprises seven described species. Two epithets have been rendered *nomen dubium*.

Oligonyx Saussure, 1869¹

= *Harpagonyx* Saussure, 1892²

= *Spanionyx* Saussure, 1892³

Oligonyx armentari **n. sp.**⁴

Oligonyx bicornis Saussure, 1869⁵

Oligonyx bidens (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Spanionyx bidens Saussure & Zehntner, 1894⁶

Oligonyx chactas **n. sp.**⁷

Oligonyx maya (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Harpagonyx maya Saussure & Zehntner, 1894⁸

Oligonyx nebulosus **n. sp.**⁹

Oligonyx undulicoxa **n. sp.**¹⁰

Harpagonyx dohrnianus Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 **nomen dubium**¹¹

Harpagonyx gryps Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 **nomen dubium**¹²

Oligonix Saussure, 1869 *lapsus calami* of *Oligonyx* Saussure, 1869

DISCUSSION

¹ Saussure (1869: 57) did not provide a formal description of *Oligonyx* when he introduced the genus. Instead, he listed the name in a key for his “Subtribe Thespites,” using it as a preliminary designation rather than a fully defined taxonomic entity. Within the main body of his text, Saussure cited the spelling as *Oligonix*. However, this discrepancy in spelling does not occur in any of Saussure’s subsequent works. In his species listings within *Oligonix*, Saussure abbreviated certain species names using the letters “G.” (e.g., *G. bicornis*) or “T.” rather than “O.”, abbreviations that do not correspond to any previously described or then currently recognized genera. These abbreviations are also considered to be typographical errors rather than indications of new or existing taxonomic classifications. When Saussure (1871: 117) later provided a formal description of this genus, his definition included species that were subsequently reassigned to distinct genera, such as *Thrinaconyx* Saussure, 1892, *Thespis* Audinet-Serville, 1831, and *Thesprotia*. Saussure (1872: 273) also incorrectly postulated that both sexes possessed well-developed wings. Later, Saussure and Zehntner (1894: 171) redefined *Oligonyx* to include species now classified under *Thespis* and *Bistanta*, while *bicornis*—the only true member of *Oligonyx*—was transferred to the newly erected genus *Spanionyx*. Further confusion ensued when Rehn (1904: 569) designated *bicornis* as the type species of *Spanionyx* while Kirby (1904: 279) designated *parva* Gmelin, 1790 as the type species for *Oligonyx*. Giglio-Tos (1915: 190) then clarified the taxonomy of this group by separating many of the confused *Thespis* species into their own genus (*Oligonicella* [now *Thespis*]) and formally designating *bicornis* as the type species for *Oligonyx*. The genus remained without an accurate description until Rivera & Svenson (2020: 66) provided such, some 151 years after its establishment.

² Saussure (1892: 122) first introduced the genus *Harpagonyx* within an identification key for Central American Thespidae, following a similar approach to his earlier introduction of *Oligonyx* two decades prior. At this point, *Harpagonyx* lacked a formal description and was distinguished

from *Oligonyx* solely by the presence of foretibial spines that were described as “curved from the base and pressed against the edge of the tibia.” No species were assigned to the genus at the time of its initial introduction. Two years later, Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 175) provided a formal description of *Harpagonyx* and included three new species within its classification: *gryps*, *dohrnianus*, and *maya*. However, none of these species were designated as the type species, leaving the genus without a clear taxonomic anchor until Rehn (1904: 568) designated *gryps* as such. Subsequent research revealed that the primary diagnostic trait that distinguished *Harpagonyx* from *Oligonyx*—the recumbent foretibial spines—was in fact a sexually dimorphic characteristic found only in males; conspecific females exhibit these spines in an erect position. Giglio-Tos (1927: 269) recognized this fact and synonymized *Harpagonyx* with *Oligonyx*, an action that was endorsed by Rehn (1935: 189) and succeeding authors.

³ In the same publication in which he introduced *Harpagonyx*, Saussure (1892: 122) also introduced the genus *Spanionyx* within the identification key for Central American Thespidae. As with *Harpagonyx*, no formal description was provided at the time. Instead, *Spanionyx* was distinguished from *Oligonyx* (and *Harpagonyx*) by the presence of “high triangular” juxtaocular lobes, in contrast to the “small rounded” lobes characteristic of the opposing genera. No species were assigned to *Spanionyx* at its initial introduction. Two years later, Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 177) provided a formal description of *Spanionyx*, describing *bidens* as a new species and transferring *bicornis* to the genus. However, neither of these species was designated as the type species, leaving the genus without an official type designation, until Rehn (1904: 569) designated *bicornis* as the type. Subsequent studies revealed that the defining characteristic of *Spanionyx*—the more prominent and triangular juxtaocular lobes—is in fact a sexually dimorphic trait found only in females; conspecific males have these lobes in a more reduced form. Giglio-Tos (1927: 269) recognized this fact and synonymized *Spanionyx* with *Oligonyx*, an action that was endorsed by Rehn (1935: 189) and succeeding authors.

Male holotype of *Oligonyx armentari* n. sp. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), anterior surface of prothoracic leg (bottom left), head capsule (bottom right).

Male holotype of *Oligonyx armentari* n. sp. Posterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top left), anterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top right), supraanal plate (bottom left), subgenital plate (bottom right).

⁴ The specific epithet “armentari” is dedicated to Maribel Armenteros in recognition of her invaluable contributions to entomology, particularly in the photographic recording of insects from Hispaniola. The presence of this undescribed species in Hispaniola was first detected by Anderson in 2020 while preparing the text “Praying Mantises of the Caribbean” (2021). While reviewing photographic observations of Mantodea from Haiti that had been uploaded to iNaturalist.com, Anderson identified a female specimen that did not correspond to any known species of Mantodea. However, as no physical specimens had yet been collected and the photograph lacked sufficient angle and resolution to be confidently diagnostic, the observation was

set aside for further investigation. Five years later, in 2025, Carlos De Soto Molinari and Maribel Armenteros photographed a male specimen at one of their light traps in Las Auyamas, Dominican Republic. Recognizing its significance, the photographers captured the specimen and later provided it to Anderson for formal study, ultimately confirming its distinction as a new species. The discovery of *armentari* not only represents the first confirmed occurrence of *Oligonyx* in the Caribbean, but also raises new questions about the biogeographical distribution of the genus, suggesting that additional undiscovered populations may exist across other islands.

Male holotype (nymph) of *Oligonyx bicornis*. Photo authored by CMNH staff. Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva.

⁵ Saussure (1869: 71) originally described *bicornis* based on what he thought was an immature female, explicitly noting in the description that the holotype was “apterous, possibly a larva.” An analysis of the holotype photograph confirms its status as actually being a male nymph, as evidenced by its underdeveloped, thickened antennae and prominent meso/metathoracic wing

pads. In contrast, both juvenile and adult females of *Oligonyx* lack wing pads altogether, replaced by much more vestigial thoracic lobes. The type locality of the holotype is listed in Saussure’s original description as “Mexico.” However, the label on the holotype provides a more specific location: “Tehuantepec, Mexique”. Saussure (1871: 122) later clarified that two specimens were

sent to him, one from Tehuantepec [Oaxaca, Mexico] and another from Alvarado [Veracruz, Mexico]. The male nymph from Oaxaca is designated as the holotype, corroborated by the holotype label. The specimen from Veracruz has no type status, as it was not included in the original description.

Holotype illustration of *Oligonyx bicornis* Saussure, 1872: Plate 6, Figure 22.

Following the original description of *bicornis*, Saussure (1872: Plate 6, Figure 22) presented three illustrations of this species that depicted the holotype's subgenital plate, foreleg, and head capsule. Notably, the holotype is currently missing its abdominal terminalia, rendering any direct comparison between Saussure's subgenital plate illustration and the existing voucher specimen unattainable.

De Luna & Granados-Corea (2022: 8) reported an extreme northern record for *bicornis* based on a female specimen collected from Monterrey, Nuevo León, Mexico. This area is significantly farther north and well outside the typical southern Mexico range of *Oligonyx*. However, it is a region

well-suited to the documented and confirmed presence of *Bistanta campestris* Anderson, 2022. Members of *Bistanta* Anderson, 2018 and *Oligonyx* are quite similar in general habitus, with superficial separation based on the degree of development of the juxtaocular lobes. In *Oligonyx*, these lobes are well-developed, creating a strong concave outline with the vertex, while in *Bistanta*, the lobes are moderately developed, forming a weaker concave outline. Since this degree of juxtaocular lobe development can be subjective and variable, a more reliable diagnostic feature is the spination of the forefemora. *Oligonyx* bears three discoidal spines on the forefemora, whereas *Bistanta* has four. Unfortunately, the spination of the forelegs in the putative Monterrey specimen was not assessed. Additionally, the photograph of the head capsule provided by the authors shows the head tilted forward and to the left, exaggerating the prominence of the juxtaocular lobes. A proper face-forward, level view of the head capsule is necessary to accurately assess the vertex's concavity. The authors also noted that they used Saussure's antiquated and erroneous keys from the 19th century to identify the specimen to species level, further complicating the reliability of their identification. Until and unless the foreleg spination of the Monterrey specimen can be confirmed, this record should be regarded as *Bistanta campestris* rather than *Oligonyx bicornis*.

Male syntype of *Harpagonyx gryps* [now *Oligonyx bidens*] (left); female holotype of *Spanionyx bidens* [now *Oligonyx bidens*] (right). Photos authored by CMNH staff. Natural History Museum, London.

⁶ *Spanionyx bidens* was described by Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 177) from a single female holotype collected on Roatán Island, Honduras. In their original description, the authors noted differences between *bidens* and *bicornis*, specifically highlighting the much more slender habitus of *bidens*, differences in head capsule and pronotum shape, and longer foretibial spines. However, all of these differences can be explained by sexual dimorphism, as the true female of *bicornis* was not known at the time, preventing a direct comparison of female material. Consequently, the female holotype of *bidens* was contrasted against male specimens of *bicornis*, leading to these perceived differences. Recent

examination reveals that the holotype of *bidens* matches in conspecificity with the Guatemalan syntype of *gryps*. Additionally, as Rehn (1935: 190) made note of and as modern collecting efforts have confirmed, specimens of *Oligonyx* collected from Honduras are indistinguishable from those originating from Guatemala, supporting their classification as the same species. Rivera & Svenson (2020: 66) incorrectly noted that *bidens* was designated as the type species for *Spanionyx* by Rehn in 1904; Rehn (1904: 569) actually stated that *bicornis* was selected as the type.

Male holotype of *Oligonyx chactas* n. sp. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), anterior surface of prothoracic leg (bottom left), head capsule (bottom right).

Male holotype of *Oligonyx chactas* **n. sp.** Posterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top left), anterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top right), supraanal plate (bottom left), subgenital plate (bottom right).

Female allotype of *Oligonyx chactas* n. sp. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), anterior surface of prothoracic leg (bottom left), head capsule (bottom right).

Female allotype of *Oligonyx chactas* n. sp. Posterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top left), anterior surface of prothoracic tibia (top right), supraanal plate (bottom left), subgenital plate (bottom right).

⁷ This new species is believed to be precinctive to Cozumel Island, which is located off the eastern coast of the Yucatán Peninsula in Quintana Roo, Mexico. This island presents a unique biogeographic system shaped by its isolation, karstic geology, and exposure to Caribbean climatic influences. As a limestone island, Cozumel lacks significant elevation, with a largely flat terrain and lowland tropical forests adapted to shallow, nutrient-poor soils. The island's tropical

maritime climate is characterized by high humidity, consistent rainfall, and exposure to hurricanes. Due to its isolation from the mainland, Cozumel harbors a distinct assemblage of flora and fauna, allowing certain taxa to radiate into ecological niches unavailable on the mainland, promoting endemism.

Male holotype of *Harpagonyx maya*. Photo authored by CMNH staff. Natural History Museum, London.

⁸ *Harpagonyx maya* was originally described by Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 176) from a single male holotype collected in Temax, Yucatán, Mexico. At the time of description, the holotype was already damaged, missing a significant portion of its abdomen. This damage rendered the

identification keys of *Oligonyx* species by later authors, which relied heavily on the shape of the supra-anal plate, useless for *maya*.

Male holotype of *Oligonyx nebulosus* n. sp. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), anterior surface of prothoracic leg (bottom left), head capsule (bottom right).

Male holotype of *Oligonyx nebulosus* n. sp. Posterior surface of prothoracic tibia (left), anterior surface of prothoracic tibia (right).

⁹ This new species was collected by Eric van den Berghe near the Uyuca Biological Station, located at approximately 1,700 meters in the department of Francisco Morazán, Honduras. The station is situated within a montane cloud forest ecosystem that is characterized by high humidity, frequent mist, and relatively cool temperatures. This region forms part of the Central American highlands, a biogeographically significant area where

orographic uplift creates steep environmental gradients that separate lowland and montane species. The biogeographic position of Uyuca, lying within the transition zone between the Pacific and Atlantic slopes, introduces additional complexity by exposing the region to climatic influences from both watersheds, further shaping species distributions, many of which are believed to be precinctive to the area.

Male holotype of *Oligonyx undulicoxa* n. sp. Dorsal habitus (left), ventral habitus (right).

Male holotype of *Oligonyx undulicoxa* n. sp. Anterior surface of prothoracic leg (top left), head capsule (top right), posterior surface of prothoracic tibia (center left), anterior surface of prothoracic tibia (center right), supraanal plate (bottom left), subgenital plate (bottom right).

¹⁰ This new species was collected by Eric van den Berghe in Yojoa, Emerald Valley, located at approximately 740 meters in the department of Cortés, Honduras. This location lies within a transitional zone between lowland tropical rainforests and mid-elevation montane forests. This region is part of the Yojoa Lake Basin, an ecologically significant area influenced by high rainfall, humid conditions, and diverse forest types, ranging from subtropical broadleaf forests to premontane wet forests. The combination of varied topography, high humidity, and moderate elevation fosters an environment rich in biodiversity, with a mixture of species adapted to both lowland and montane conditions. One of the most important biogeographical features of Yojoa is its proximity to Lake Yojoa, the largest freshwater lake in Honduras. The lake's presence creates a unique microclimate, moderating temperature fluctuations and contributing to consistent high moisture levels that sustain dense, year-round vegetation.

¹¹ Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 176) described *Harpagonyx dohrnianus* based on a male holotype from Guatemala that they had sourced from the Dohrn collection. The German entomologist Carl August Dohrn (1806–1892) was particularly known for his contributions to the study of Coleoptera. While his primary focus was on European beetles, he also described species from other regions, including Central America, from specimens that were sent to him by other collectors. Dohrn's extensive insect collection and his large library were donated to the Stettin Museum. Unfortunately, much of this collection was destroyed during World War II, leading to the loss of many type specimens and resulting in several species he described being treated as *nomen dubium* due to the absence of these types. The holotype of *dohrnianus* is believed to be one of these lost specimens, as its current state is entirely unknown. Ehrmann (2002: 246) listed the holotype of *Harpagonyx dohrnianus* as being deposited at the Deutsches Entomologisches Institut (DEI), now the Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut (SDEI). However, the author's personal communication with the curator

of the insect collection at SDEI confirms that they do not possess this type specimen or any other material of *Harpagonyx dohrnianus*. Additionally, Petersen & Gaedike do not include *dohrnianus* in their type catalogue for the SDEI.

Rehn (1935: 190) suggested that *bidens* likely represents the unrecognized female of *dohrnianus* and noted that *dohrnianus* has page precedence over *bidens* within Saussure & Zehntner's original publication, and thus *dohrnianus* should take priority as the valid name. However, the taxonomic identity of *dohrnianus* remains highly uncertain due to several factors, warranting its designation as a *nomen dubium* rather than a synonym of *bidens*. First, the holotype is lost, eliminating the possibility of direct morphological comparison with newly examined material. Without a reference specimen, the application of this name to any population becomes speculative. Second, the original description provided by Saussure & Zehntner is vague, lacking diagnostic characters essential for distinguishing species within *Oligonyx*, such as prozona-to-metazona ratios, forefemoral shape, and forefemoral maculation patterns. The absence of these key features means that the description could apply broadly to multiple species within the genus, rendering it insufficient for precise identification. Third, the type locality is simply listed as "Guatemala", an overly broad designation that encompasses numerous ecological zones and potential species diversity. Without a more precise locality, it is impossible to correlate *dohrnianus* with any particular population. Furthermore, while additional *Oligonyx* material from Central America is now available, including several new species, there is no strong justification to assign such material to *dohrnianus* given the lack of defining characters in the original description. In light of these issues—the lost type, vague description, and ambiguous locality—*Harpagonyx dohrnianus* cannot be reliably identified and should be regarded as a *nomen dubium*, preventing further misapplication of the name and ensuring taxonomic clarity within *Oligonyx*.

Male pronotum of *Harpagonyx gryps* [now *Oligonyx bicornis*] syntype from Atoyac, Veracruz, Mexico. Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva (left); male pronotum of *Harpagonyx gryps* [now *Oligonyx bidens*] syntype from Alta Verapaz, Guatemala. Natural History Museum, London (right). Photos authored by CMNH staff.

¹² Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 176) originally described *Harpagonyx gryps* based on a series of three adult male syntypes. These specimens were collected from distinct ecoregions, each at different times and by different collectors. Two of the syntypes originated from the tropical dry forest ecoregion of Veracruz, Mexico, specifically from Atoyac and Xalapa, while the third syntype was collected from the much more varied ecoregion of Alta Verapaz, Guatemala. Currently, the syntype from Xalapa is missing, leaving only the specimens from Atoyac and Alta Verapaz available for study. A detailed examination of photographs of these remaining syntypes has revealed a significant difference in their pronotal dimensions. The Guatemalan specimen from Alta Verapaz exhibits a markedly more elongated pronotum compared to the Atoyac specimen from Veracruz. The metazona length to prozona length in the Alta Verapaz syntype is 2.4, whereas the Atoyac syntype is measured at 2.1. Saussure recognized these differences and briefly described the Veracruz syntype as a variation, characterized by a “pronotum slightly shorter, granulated; anterior coxae touching its base.” It is now evident that the variant specimen noted by Saussure represents a

distinct species from the Guatemalan syntype, indicating that the syntypes from the two distinct ecoregions belong to separate taxonomic entities rather than a single, variable species. Since the *gryps* specimen from Veracruz matches the holotype of *bicornis*, the two names have been historically synonymized, as recognized by Giglio-Tos (1927: 270). However, because the type series also contains a representative of *bidens*, *gryps* was never taxonomically valid as a single entity. A formal lectotype designation could theoretically resolve the issue by restricting *gryps* to one of the syntypes but both surviving syntypes are assigned to valid species names (*bicornis* and *bidens*), making such a designation arbitrary and unnecessary. Since *gryps* was originally applied to a mixed taxon, it cannot be considered a junior synonym of both *bicornis* and *bidens*, nor can it be reliably assigned to either species. To maintain taxonomic stability within *Oligonyx*, the most appropriate resolution is to treat *gryps* as a *nomen dubium* and suppress its use. This prevents further confusion and ensures that valid species names—*bicornis* and *bidens*—are applied consistently without unnecessary ambiguity.

LIVE SPECIMEN OBSERVATIONS

01, *Oligonyx armentari* holotype male. Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic 06.02.2024
(Photo: Carlos De Soto Molinari)

02, *Oligonyx armentari* holotype male. Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic 06.02.2024
(Photo: Carlos De Soto Molinari)

03, *Oligonyx armentari* holotype male. Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic 06.02.2024
(Photo: Carlos De Soto Molinari)

04, *Oligonyx armentari* female. Wynne Farm Ecological Reserve, Ouest, Haiti 08.26.20 (Photo: René Durocher)

05, *Oligonyx bicornis* male. Catemaco, Veracruz, Mexico 05.29.22 (Photo: Jorge Eduardo Rojas Soriano)

06, *Oligonyx bicornis* male. Xalapa, Veracruz, Mexico 09.30.24 (Photo: Benjamin Munoz)

07, *Oligonyx bicornis* female. Manlio Fabio Altamirano, Veracruz, Mexico 05.24.20 (Photo: Robb Navarro)

08, *Oligonyx bicornis* female demonstrating impaling prey capture. Tamasopo, San Luis Potosi, Mexico 07.21.16 (Photo: Juan Cruzado Cortes)

09, *Oligonyx bidens* male. Cayo, Belize 08.11.22 (Photo: Jorge Castellanos)

10, *Oligonyx bidens* female. Bacalar, Quintana Roo, Mexico 01.19.23 (Photo: Daniel Moreno)

11, *Oligonyx maya* male. Temax, Yucatan, Mexico 08.31.24 (Photo: Martin Riestra Morales)

12, *Oligonyx maya* female. Merida, Yucatan, Mexico 11.05.20 (Photo: Martin Riestra Morales)

13, *Oligonyx nebulosus* male. San Antonio de Oriente, Francisco Morazan, Honduras (Photo: Jennifer Estrada)

14, *Oligonyx nebulosus* male. Danli, El Paraiso, Honduras 02.09.25 (Photo: Claudia Mejia de Mendoza)

15, *Oligonyx nebulosus* female. Patulul, Suchitepeque, Guatemala 05.21.24 (Photo: John Sullivan)

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